

D7.8 – PROGRAMME AND SUMMARY/OUTLINE OF THE PROJECT ADVANCEMENTS AND DECISIONS TAKEN AT THE 3RD AND 4TH STEERING COMMITTEE MEETING

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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Delivery date	
Dissemination level	Public

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GeneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326.

101094326 – GeneSys – D.7.8

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

Project Acronym	GeneSys
Agreement number	101094326
Project Full Title	gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems
Funding Scheme	Horizon Europe

Deliverable Information

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Abstract	

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Date	Version	Contributor(s)	Description	Supervision

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1. INTRODUCTION: THE PROJECT GENESYS AND ITS TIMELINE

Led by the National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies (CNR-IRPPS), the project **gEneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems)** aims to contribute to equal participation of women and men in the energy sector and to mainstream the SDG5 goals (concerning gender equality) into the SDG7 goals. With this goal in mind, the project envisages research activities to better understand the relationships between gender and energy transition/transformation in the extant scientific knowledge and knowledge communities (WP1) and to interrogate this relationships through ad-hoc designed surveys to knowledgeable actors ("actors of change") as well as to lay citizens ("recipients of change") (WP1 and WP2). The project acknowledges the relevance of international cooperation with African partners for the realization of a fair and just energy transition dedicating an entire WP (WP4) to identifying the needs and opportunities in Africa to advance women in energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders. Moreover, the project plans for practical activities to mainstream the project's key themes into the students' and teachers' training and curricula (WP3). Finally, the project seeks to pave the way for a sustainable impact by the development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions (WP5).

The project started officially on February 1st, 2023. In accordance with the project timeline, the 3rd Steering Committee meeting was convened in Kraków at the midpoint of Month 16 (June 18th-19th, 2024), summoning the representatives from all partner organizations.

During the project meeting, partners provided updates on the progress of ongoing activities related to the Work Package (WP) tasks (T1.5; T2.1/T2.2/T2.3; T3.1/T3.2/T3.3; T4.2; T5.1/T5.3/T5.4). In addition to i) reviewing and discussing the progress achieved, the agenda included key objectives, including to ii) deliberating on dissemination and outreach strategies, particularly in relation to organizing the Joint Conference in October 2024 and the Autumn School in Venice in the project's third year (2025); iii) planning an additional project meeting in the coming months.

Among the main decisions taken, it was agreed to organize a Joint Conference in October 2024 in Brussels, bringing together two Horizon Europe projects to promote the integration of gender equality objective into technologically focused solutions to societal challenges. Furthermore, a fourth project meeting was scheduled to take place in London approximately six months later, despite not being originally included in the project timeline.

This additional meeting was deemed essential to enhance collaboration among partners in integrating project results during the final year. For this reason, section 6, which goes into more detail about the meeting held in London from February 16–20, 2025, will follow.

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

In the months after the third meeting, an online review meeting with the policy officers held on July 11th 2024. Concurrently, research activities outlined in WP1, WP2, and WP3 began, including:

- The launch of a survey on stakeholder organisations in sustainable system (T1.5. Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems), led by CNR.
- The launch of a survey and case studies examining citizen's behaviours and orientations towards energy transition (T2.1. Exploring intersectional power-gender relations; and T2.3 Case study analyses), led by Fraunhofer.
- The realization of focus group interviews with lectures and student (STEM and SSH) in Poland, Germany, United Kingdom and Italy (T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems), led by UJ.

2. THE THIRD PROJECT MEETING IN KRAKÓW

The third project meeting (see annex 1 and 2 for the full agenda and [list of participants](#)) took place in Kraków on 18th and 19th June 2024, spanning one full day and one half day. The meeting aimed to achieve the following objectives:

- (i) Set out a plan and establish collaborations for the upcoming tasks;
- (ii) Review the project's status, including the ethics check and associated blocked activities (WP7);
- (iii) Taking stock of the work performed and identifying gaps or unaddressed issue (all WPs);
- (iv) Explore opportunities for internal and external collaborations, as well as strategies for disseminating results (WP6);
- (v) Address management and coordination matters (WP7), including the results of the first Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) survey, the financial report, and discussions on the technical reports and the review meeting.

As for point (i), the project coordinator requested that task leaders prepare PowerPoint presentations outlining: (1) the task's work plan and proposed timeline, (2) objectives

and target groups, (3) methodology, (4) key findings, and (5) next steps. A list of these presentations is available in Annex 3.

Regarding the second point (ii), CNR provided an overview of the project's status, with a particular focus on the Ethic check, which at that time had halted all activities involving human participants (Tasks 1.5, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 3.3). CNR also outlined strategies to resolve this issue through the CNR Ethics Committee, including obtaining clearance and fulfilling additional requirements such as a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).

Concerning point (iii), WP leaders presented the activities carried out thus far, followed by a discussion in which all partners provided relevant feedback and suggestions.

For the point (iv), the WP6 leader presented an overview of activities carried out during October 2023 – June 2024, along with proposed dissemination strategies and outreach initiatives. Two key dissemination efforts were defined. First, the Joint Conference on the theme of Gender Knowledge for fair and Just Energy Transitions. This event will occur in October 2024 at the Scotland House in Brussels. Second, a proposed ISR Special Issue incorporating findings from WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Additionally, as part of WP6, an initial outline of the Autumn School—scheduled for October 2025 in Venice—was presented. After introducing the venue, the session discussed the initial collaboration efforts between CNR and VIU regarding the call for applications, student selection, and logistical arrangements. The session also included a broader discussion among all partners on the training modules and content to be developed in the coming months.

Regarding the last point (v), under WP7 Management and Coordination, the results of the Monitorign and Evaluation (M&E) survey – distributed to all partners (including senior and junior staff), a few weeks prior to the Kraków meeting – were presented and discussed.

A subsequent presentation focused on the financial report, providing an overview of RP1 budget distribution among partners and required actions on the platform

Additionally, the meeting included a discussion session on the structure and other organizational aspects of the upcoming review meeting, scheduled for July 11, 2024, involving the monitors and policy officers.

As a final decision, partners agreed to schedule an additional project meeting in London at the beginning of 2025.

3. KEY DECISIONS TAKEN

At the end of the meeting, the team agreed on the following decisions/list of actions:

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

1. Next steering committee meeting will be hosted by Imperial in London in February 2025 (see section 6 on The fourth project meeting in London);
2. Joint Conference Integrating Gender Equality Objectives into Energy and Deep Tech Fields for Inclusive and Sustainable Future, 22 October 2024 Scotland House, Brussels (see details here: <https://genesys-project.eu/events/>)
3. List of publication and open access policy for all the projects results
4. Plan the future project activities following a shared tasks distribution accordingly to the WP ppt presentation.

4. WAY FORWARD

On the short term, the gEneSys meeting sets the start of a number of activities that were planned ahead in 2024. A common task plan was drafted and shared with partners to coordinate the project activities.

5. ANNEX

5.1. ANNEX 1: List of attendees to the project third meeting

Commentato [MF1]: Non ho il foglio firme di Cracovia

5.2. ANNEX 2: Project Meeting Full Agenda

gEneSys - Project Meeting - Agenda

June, 18th and 19th 2024

Institute of Sociology at the Jagiellonian University
room 61 (1st Gate)

Grodzka 52, 31-044 Kraków, Poland

gEneSys

June 18TH

9:30	Registration and welcome coffee
9:45	Welcome from the Director of the Institute of Sociology, prof. Marta Smagacz-Pozniemska WP7/8 - Project status: Ethics check, delay, postponement - CNR coordination team and partners (30 minutes)
10:15	WP1 updates – T1.5 Gendered assessment of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems – CNR (15 minutes)
10:30	WP2 updates – T.2.1/2.2/2.3 – Exploring gendered intersectional patterns in citizen's behaviors- CaRRi (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (15 minutes)
11:00	WP3 updates – T3.1/3.2/3.3 – Development of concrete solution to advance women in energy transition (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (15 minutes)
11:30	Coffee break
12:00	WP4 updates – T4.2 Identify the needs and opportunities to advance women in Africa as energy transition researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders (20 minutes)
12:20	WP5 updates – 5.1/5.3/5.4 Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions (30 minutes)
12:50	Lunch (Corleone, Posańska 19)
14:30	WP6 – Autumn School – Venice 5-11 October 2025 (Objectives/targets/trainers/disseminations) (40 minutes)
15:10	WP6 – gEneSys conference organization (Brussels 17 th October) partner feedback and synergies with EUI including Light on Women energy base (30 minutes)
15:40	Publication plan: WP leaders report on planned published research output including the Special Issue proposal (40 minutes)
16:20	Final discussion (40 minutes)
17:00	Closure
19:00	Social dinner (Cafe Organizacja, pl. Juliusza Kossaka 1)

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

09:30	WP7 - Financial report RP1 (45 minutes)
10:15	WP7 - Technical report and review meeting preparation including review of monitors profile (July 11 th <u>online</u>) (45 minutes)
11:00	Coffee break
11:30	WP7 - Monitoring and evaluation (20 minutes)
11:50	Final discussion – setting next project meeting date and venue (70 minutes)
13:00	Lunch (Corleone, Polonia 19)
15:00 Guided Walk "Women of Krakow" (+/- 2 hours)	

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

5.3. ANNEX 3: gEneSys 3rd meeting power point presentations on preliminary results

WP3
Development of Concrete Solutions to Advance Women in Energy Transition

WP3 Tasks

- T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among young women and gender equality (01/2020 - 01/2022)
- T3.2 Analyse and compare the existing policies, identify gaps and develop the Road Map for the research areas (01/2020 - 01/2021)
- T3.3 Develop the guidelines, of women in energy transition in various EU countries
- T3.4 Offer educational resources, dissemination, knowledge, education and Higher Education (01/2020 - 01/2022)
- T3.5 Offer gender equality guidelines energy transition in research, innovation and Higher Education (01/2020 - 01/2022)

Partners' involvement in WP3

Partner	Con. to WP3
1. UNICEF	10.00
1.1. RWI	10.00
2. ICI	10.00
3. ENCK	10.00
4. European	10.00
5. A&S Research	10.00
6. Energy Council	10.00
7. Gender	10.00
8. Gender	10.00
Total Involvement	100.00

WP3: General description

Objectives: 01/2020 - 01/2022

Impact: 01/2020 - 01/2022

Results: 01/2020 - 01/2022

Deliverables: 01/2020 - 01/2022

Milestones: 01/2020 - 01/2022

WP3 Deliverables & Milestones

Deliverables:

- D3.1 - Roadmap for the research areas (01/2020 - 01/2021)
- D3.2 - Policy brief on research and gender equality energy transition (01/2021)
- D3.3 - Roadmap of gender equality energy transition (01/2021)
- D3.4 - Guidelines and best practices for research and gender equality (01/2021)
- D3.5 - Guidelines and best practices for research and gender equality (01/2021)

Milestones:

- M3.1 - Awareness raising (01/2020)
- M3.2 - Dissemination and training on gender equality in energy transition (01/2020)

T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among school-age students (01/2020 - 01/2022)

Objectives:

- T3.1.1 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.2 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.3 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.4 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.5 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.6 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.7 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.8 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.9 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps
- T3.1.10 Analyse the existing energy transition policies and identify the existing gaps

WP3 Objectives

- Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among young women and gender equality
- Analyse and compare the existing policies, identify gaps and develop the Road Map for the research areas (01/2020 - 01/2021)
- Develop the guidelines, of women in energy transition in various EU countries
- Offer educational resources, dissemination, knowledge, education and Higher Education (01/2020 - 01/2022)
- Offer gender equality guidelines energy transition in research, innovation and Higher Education (01/2020 - 01/2022)

Partners' involvement in WP3

Partner	T3.1	T3.2	T3.3	T3.4
1. UNICEF	100%	100%	100%	100%
1.1. RWI	100%	100%	100%	100%
2. ICI	100%	100%	100%	100%
3. ENCK	100%	100%	100%	100%
4. European	100%	100%	100%	100%
5. A&S Research	100%	100%	100%	100%
6. Energy Council	100%	100%	100%	100%
7. Gender	100%	100%	100%	100%
8. Gender	100%	100%	100%	100%

T3.1 Sample selection/methodology

Partner Contact Details:

- 1. UNICEF (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - unicef@unicef.org
- 1.1. RWI (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - rw@rw.ac.uk
- 2. ICI (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - ici@ici.org
- 3. ENCK (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - enck@enck.org
- 4. European (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - european@european.org
- 5. A&S Research (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - asr@asr.org
- 6. Energy Council (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - ec@ec.org
- 7. Gender (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - gender@gender.org
- 8. Gender (Gender Equality, Education and Learning) - gender@gender.org

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

T3.2 Sample selection/methodology

How we got here:

1. Analysis of primary school (7-8 grade) and secondary school (9-12 grade) curricula searching for keywords: Energy, Environment, Materials, Robotics, Physics, Informatics and Research.
2. We then selected the following subjects: Physics, Geography, History, Social Studies, Life Sciences, Engineering, Chemistry, History and the Present.
3. Initial search in the library – using the chapters and abstract pages.
4. The Jagiellonian University Library performed OCR scanning and digitization.
5. Importing the data into MAXQDA.

Max QDA 12.6.0 (64-bit) | 10.10.2018 10:00:00

T3.1 Further steps

- 1. Comparison: international (USA, UK, Canada, EU)
- 2. Comparison: interdisciplinarity (STEM, Arts, Humanities)
- 3. Comparison: interdisciplinarity (STEM, Arts, Humanities)
- 4. Comparison: interdisciplinarity (STEM, Arts, Humanities)

10.10.2018 10:00:00

T3.3 Analysis of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition (Months 24-30)

10.10.2018 10:00:00

T3.1 Coding tree

T3.2 Analysis and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the field/sub-field vs. the renewable energy sectors (Months 8-24)

10.10.2018 10:00:00

WPs Towards the common publication

10.10.2018 10:00:00

T3.1 Preliminary observations

- 1. Gender inequality and gender issues absent in national school curricula.
- 2. Energy and environment topics present in national school curricula.
- 3. Gender inequality and gender issues present in national school curricula.
- 4. Gender inequality and gender issues present in national school curricula.

10.10.2018 10:00:00

T3.2 Guidelines for FGI

- 1. Project leader (Co-PIs): Prof. Dr. Barbara Glensk, Prof. Dr. Barbara Glensk
- 2. Project leader (Co-PIs): Prof. Dr. Barbara Glensk, Prof. Dr. Barbara Glensk
- 3. Project leader (Co-PIs): Prof. Dr. Barbara Glensk, Prof. Dr. Barbara Glensk

10.10.2018 10:00:00

Main findings

Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy (LEAP-RE)

- Involves 65 research partners from both regions, working together to develop innovative renewable energy solutions and foster long-term collaboration in renewable energy.
- Expected to reduce Regeneration by aligning existing bilateral and multilateral frameworks.

The UK Partnership for Accelerated Climate Transition (UK PACT)

- Efforts to transition to low-carbon, climate-resilient economies.
- Focuses on supporting the development of renewable energy projects and promoting sustainable energy stores across the countries.

• Has the Gender, Equality and Social Inclusion (GESI) considerations as an integral part of the programme and in Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa.

Objectives and methods

- Review the past and still active research and innovation cooperation programmes funded in Africa, supported through EU or European country funding, to identify if and how they involved and benefited women.
- Identify the needs and opportunities in Africa to advance women in energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders.
- Identify concrete actors, instruments, and mechanisms to operationalise the European Parliament's recommendations for cooperation on SDGs implementation.
- Analyse how the concepts of equity, inclusion, justice, and fairness are interpreted by students in Africa, especially in the context of SDG7 targets.
- Assess collaborative areas on energy transition in terms of policy alignment, gender mainstreaming and financial analysis.

Main findings

- There is a critical gap in understanding the gender-energy nexus in most partnerships.
- Traditional energy sector perspectives often overlook social dimensions, including gender dynamics.
- A lack of gender-disaggregated data and standardized methodologies hampers comprehensive research.
- Horizon Europe plays a significant role in supporting these efforts in Africa.
- Integration of gender considerations is essential for equitable energy transition outcomes.

Main findings

Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP)

- Focus on sustainable energy services, renewable energy, and energy efficiency.
- Part of the Joint Africa-EU Strategy with a significant investment package.

Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETP)

- Global collaboration for transitioning from fossil energy to clean energy.
- Partnerships with South Africa and Senegal with substantial financial support.

Climate Change and Sustainable Energy Partnership (CCSE)

- Joint AU-EU research and innovation partnership.
- Supports renewable energy and energy efficiency in Africa.

CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

- The EU-Africa partnership is crucial for sustainable development and gender equality.
- Collaborative efforts are needed to bridge gaps and enhance capacity in energy and gender areas for a more inclusive and sustainable energy transition.
- Continued focus on gender-sensitive policies and interdisciplinary research is essential for a sustainable and inclusive energy future.
- Partnerships should consider cultural, social and economic dimensions.

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

WP 5 Deliverables

Deliverable	Start	End	Responsible	Status
D5.1	2023-01-01	2023-03-31	IMP	Completed
D5.2	2023-04-01	2023-06-30	IMP	In Progress
D5.3	2023-07-01	2023-09-30	IMP	Not Started
D5.4	2023-10-01	2023-12-31	IMP	Not Started

Task 5.1 identification of criteria for the selection of a model pathway. Task Leader: IC. Contribution: S1, WP5 (S1-S4, S11)

To identify and define the criteria to 'model' pathways for the selection of a model pathway. The criteria will be used to filter the pathways for the selection of a model pathway. The criteria will be used to filter the pathways for the selection of a model pathway. The criteria will be used to filter the pathways for the selection of a model pathway.

Draft July 15

WPS Activities

Activity	Responsible	Duration
S.1.1 Quality check of deliverables for selection of a model pathway	Task Leader: IC, Contribution: S1, WP5 (S1-S4, S11)	04/2023-05/2023
S.1.2 Improving general perspective on energy equity	Task Leader: IC, Contribution: S1, WP5 (S1-S4, S11)	04/2023-05/2023
S.1.3 Improving general perspective on energy equity (continued)	Task Leader: IC, Contribution: S1, WP5 (S1-S4, S11)	04/2023-05/2023
S.1.4 Coherence of general and energy of a model pathway with existing technology. Task	Task Leader: IC, Contribution: S1, WP5 (S1-S4, S11)	04/2023-05/2023
S.1.5 Model pathway selection criteria	Task Leader: IC, Contribution: S1, WP5 (S1-S4, S11)	04/2023-05/2023

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Theories supporting gender and social equity and energy transitions

- Intersectional Justice Theory** (Crenshaw, 1991): This theory emphasizes the interconnectedness of various forms of oppression and advocates for a holistic approach to social justice that addresses the experiences of marginalized groups.
- Just Transition Theory** (ILO, 2015): This theory focuses on the need for a transition to sustainable development that is fair and equitable, taking into account the needs and interests of all workers, communities, and other stakeholders.

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Intersectionality Theory:

- Intersectionality** is a concept that recognizes the ways in which different forms of oppression (such as race, gender, and class) intersect and influence each other.
- Intersectionality** is a framework for understanding the experiences of marginalized groups, particularly women of color, who face multiple forms of discrimination.
- Intersectionality** is a theory that emphasizes the interconnectedness of various forms of oppression and advocates for a holistic approach to social justice.

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Examples of pathways:

- Global Energy Assessment, 2012**
- Delmas-Mathiey and Berthelette (2015)**: This study explores the role of energy efficiency in the transition to a low-carbon economy, highlighting the importance of energy efficiency in reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

IMPERIAL

Cont.

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Principles, criteria, indicators

- Principles** are the guiding values that inform the development and implementation of a policy or program.
- Criteria** are the standards or benchmarks used to evaluate the performance of a policy or program.
- Indicators** are the measurable variables used to track progress and assess the impact of a policy or program.

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Synthesis of factors to consider when selecting indicators:

- Relevance**: The indicator should be directly related to the objectives of the policy or program.
- Measurability**: The indicator should be quantifiable and easy to measure.
- Availability**: The data needed to calculate the indicator should be readily available.
- Timeliness**: The indicator should be updated regularly to reflect current trends.
- Cost-effectiveness**: The indicator should be affordable and easy to implement.

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steerin committee meeting

- Example criteria and indicators for Employment and Economic Participation**
- Employment**
 - Number of jobs created in the energy sector
 - Number of jobs created in the energy sector by gender
 - Number of jobs created in the energy sector by age group
 - Number of jobs created in the energy sector by education level
 - Number of jobs created in the energy sector by region
 - Entrepreneurship**
 - Number of new businesses created in the energy sector
 - Number of new businesses created in the energy sector by gender
 - Number of new businesses created in the energy sector by age group
 - Number of new businesses created in the energy sector by education level
 - Number of new businesses created in the energy sector by region
 - Income**
 - Median household income in the energy sector
 - Median household income in the energy sector by gender
 - Median household income in the energy sector by age group
 - Median household income in the energy sector by education level
 - Median household income in the energy sector by region
 - Skills and Competence**
 - Number of people with skills in the energy sector
 - Number of people with skills in the energy sector by gender
 - Number of people with skills in the energy sector by age group
 - Number of people with skills in the energy sector by education level
 - Number of people with skills in the energy sector by region

15.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EJA recommendations for research, innovation, and education to achieve the mission of energy transition. Months 15-30

• TS 3 will advise the EJA recommendations of their needs, research, innovation, and education to develop gender equality and digital and regional policies, and other areas related to the energy transition. The gender-related research and innovation for achieving economic, social, and environmental energy transition.

15.3.4 Co-creation of guidelines and analysis of scenarios with a backing-up methodology. Task Leader: IC, Coordinators: Paris, OCE, ENEA | (M15-M30)

The task will define the methodology for the co-creation of guidelines and scenarios with the stakeholders (public, private, and academic) and will define the methodology for the co-creation of guidelines and scenarios with the stakeholders (public, private, and academic) and will define the methodology for the co-creation of guidelines and scenarios with the stakeholders (public, private, and academic).

Workshops

- Need to coordinate with other proposed workshops (W7) for 2025
- Set if objectives are similar
- Dedicated workshops for backing-up

Thank You !

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steerin committee meeting

<p>WP6 Dissemination and Impact Activities during October 2023-June 2024</p> <p>European Publisher: PORTIA gEneSys</p> <p>Co-IPs: PORTIA, Fraunhofer, ENEA, Imperial College London, AMSWS, etc.</p>	<p>Key activities during October 2023 – June 2024</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website – 2500 unique visitors, 5200 page views • Promoting June webinar - 450 unique visitors • EUSEW 2024 – proposed session not accepted (no gender sessions at all); 200 registered participants contacted via the platform's Message page • gEneSys – CINEA joint webinar, December 2023 • GISTER Gender Innovation Indicators webinar, December 2023 (Gill Allwood & Mario Marin-Gambo speakers) • Gender Summit 24 – Exhibition Booth • EUI – Lights on Women – on-going talks about collaboration; survey of members (400), will join the Conference in October • gEneSys - Leap-Re – joint webinar + direct contact with some projects, will join the conference • Conference – 17 October, Brussels
<p>Targets for the Next Period</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conference • Fresh content for website • EUI Survey Lights on Women DB + networks of professional women • ISR Special Issue • EUSEW 2025 session • LEAP-RE – additional webinars • Re-engage with the parliament and the Commission (post election changes) • Re-engage with GS networks in Africa (for WP4) • Workshop on SDGs – EU-Africa (T6.2/T6.4) • Workshop on (holistic) education policy, and practice, for energy transition (T6.2/T6.3) 	<p>The Conference: 17 October, Brussels, Scotland House</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theme: Gender Knowledge for Fair and Just Energy Transition • 130 people, 10:00 – 17:30 • gEneSys results panel session • Policy panel session (Commission (DG RTD, DG EAC, DG Budget), Parliament (FEMM, EPRS, ENER, ITRE), Science Europe, EUA...) • Advisory Board panel session • Joint Panel session (LEAP-RE, EUI...) • Networking/Posters • (another 'final' conference before project ends in Rome)
<p>ISR Special Issue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender knowledge in the European energy transition policies (WP1/WP2) • Perceptions of gender roles, norms and equality among energy researchers and citizens (WP1/WP2) • Credible energy transition pathways through coordinated institution-level policies (WP3/WP4) • Gender-sensitivity in energy education among pre-school and school-age students (WP3) • Gender knowledge in education policy, researcher training, and research priorities (WP3/WP5) • Comparative analysis of scientific and grey literature on gender-energy nexus (WP3) • Ontological models with gender aspects for energy transformation (WP1) • Socio-demographic characteristics on engagement with energy transition policies (WP1/WP5) 	<p>Thank You !</p> <p>Co-IPs: PORTIA, Fraunhofer, ENEA, Imperial College London, AMSWS, etc.</p>

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

Project status: Ethics check, and blocked activities

- gEneSys about halfway, July 2024 - M18
- Following EC ethics check data collection involving humans blocked, affected tasks 1.5, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 3.3
- All preparatory work done and ready to restart data collection
- A delay has been accumulated and need to be

Ethics Deliverable and its revisions

- First Ethics Check Report: Received in December 2023. Add several info to the deliverable; to get an Ethical Clearance from an ethic commission external to the project.
- We collected the required information, and we updated the Deliverable. We asked an ethical clearance from the CNR Ethics Committee.
- The revised deliverable ready in January but the clearance just arrived in mid-April. Also, the clearance was subordinated to several additional requirements, including a DPIA.

Ethics Deliverable and its revisions

- Second Ethics Check Report: Received on 24-April 2024. The Commission's Ethic Expert agreed with the CNR commission on the necessity to perform a DPIA. Plus required other additional information.
- CeRRI performed a DPIA while CNR collected the information required and updated the deliverable.

Ethics Deliverable and its revisions

- On 14-May the DPIA was sent to CNR DPO that need to validate it.
- With few revisions we get the validation by CNR DPO last week and along with the new version of the deliverable to be sent to CNR Ethic Committee and to Project officer in coming days.
- All the requirements have then been fulfilled but the Commission's ethic expert will need to revise
- We expect to close the full process in September

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

Our monitors' profiles

Nthabiseng MOHLAKOANA

- Delft University
- **Cooperates on gender mainstreaming policies governance mechanisms**
- **Chairwoman**
- **WPA Governance of collective energy systems** (European research project: [GEM](#))
- **Chairwoman of working group on energy efficiency and energy storage**
- **Expanding energy transition (took in collaboration with my energy)** [Contribution to Energy Transition](#) - TU Delft
- **Member of task force** (to support in South African municipalities and community for [Sustainable Energy Roadmap for Association of Municipalities in S.E.Countries](#))

Our monitors' profiles

Vesna KOLEGA

- EU Green Leaf Expert for Climate Change and Energy Performance, EU Green Capital Expert for Energy Performance
- In-depth knowledge of energy legislation. Member of numerous working groups for transposition of EU energy policies and legislation into the national legislative framework.
- Member EC Joint Research Centre Working Group for Development of EU official methodologies for development, implementation and verification of Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) of Cities and Municipalities.
- **SUSTAINABLE ENERGY ROADMAP FOR ASSOCIATION OF MUNICIPALITIES IN SEE COUNTRIES** [Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Development Goals-2.pdf](#) [SustainableEnergy.com](#)

Policy officers participating in the review meeting

- **Joana Simão Costa**, Legal Officer in Directorate General for Energy
- **Jeanne Lenders**, Policy Officer in the Gender Sector Directorate General for Research and Innovation
- **Orlane Gilloz**, Policy Officer in the Gender Sector Directorate General for Research and Innovation

What next?

- **Share your ppt, thanks to those already did!**
- **Rehearsal meeting on July 10th, 10.00**
- **Review meeting July 11th (9.30 –13.30 agenda will follow)**

gEneSys consortium in Kraków

6. THE FOURTH PROJECT MEETING IN LONDON

The fourth project meeting (see annexes 1 and 2 for the full agenda and list of participants) occurred on 17th and 19th February 2025. This meeting included an additional day beyond the usual schedule in other meetings to allow partners to coordinate within working teams for effective result integration.

The meeting aimed to achieve the following objectives:

- i. Set out a plan and establish collaborations for the upcoming tasks;
- ii. Review the project's status (WP7);
- iii. Taking stock of the work performed and identifying gaps or unaddressed issues (all WPs);
- iv. Explore opportunities for internal and external collaborations, as well as strategies for disseminating results and dissemination and synergies between modules of the Autumn School (WP6);
- v. Address management and coordination matters (WP7), including the results of the first Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) survey, and the financial report.
- vi. Internal workshop for integrating WPs results

For point (i), the project coordinator requested that task leaders prepare PowerPoint presentations covering: (1) the task's work plan and proposed timeline, (2) objectives and target groups, (3) methodology, (4) findings, and (5) next steps. A complete list of these presentations can be found in Annex 7.

Regarding the point (ii), CNR provided an overview of the project's status, summarizing the activities completed in 2023/2024 and those still needed for 2025. In this last year, efforts will focus on consolidating results and maximizing the impact of the knowledge produced. Key outputs will include a policy paper, EJA recommendations, guideline for curricula, SDG integration, guideline for text books, a toolbox, an autumn school and a final conference. Another topic discussed was the project amendment, which includes a three-month extension, postponing the end of gEneSys to April 2026.

Concerning point (iii), WP leaders presented the activities carried out thus far, followed by a discussion in which all partners provided relevant feedback and suggestions. In particular, the final results of some WPs were presented, while forthcoming deliverables for others were outlined. Completed activities include a survey conducted with

research staff (WP1), a survey on citizen's behaviours and attitudes toward the energy transition (WP2), and focus group interviews with students and lectures from both SSH and in StEM disciplines (WP3).

For the point (iv), the WP6 leader presented potential dissemination networks, including the final conference, which is scheduled to take place between the second and third week of April 2026 in Brussels. The discussion covered possible keynote speakers and event format, which is expected to consist of a half-day dedicated to research outputs and another half-day focused on policy discussion and a round table session. Special attention was given to the Horizon Europe Results Booster Services, with a proposed timeline for implementation.

Additionally, as part of WP6, CNR provided an update on upcoming Autumn School, scheduled for October 2025 in Venice. The updates included information on the number of applicants, logistics details, and a first draft of the programs and modules, which will be coordinated among all partners.

Regarding the last point (v), under WP7 Management and Coordination, the results of the Monitorign and Evaluation (M&E) survey – distributed to all partners (including senior and junior staff), a few weeks prior to the London meeting – were presented. These results were then discussed in a roundtable session.

A subsequent presentation focused on the publication plan, covering submitted and accepted publications, as well as those still under review by scientific journals.

The third and last day of the meeting was dedicated to an internal workshop for intregating WPs results (vi). The session began with a presentation on the backcasting methodology, led by Imperial, followed by a syntesis of more relevant WPs results by all partners.

Afterwards participants were divided into three smaller groups, ensuring that members from different teams were mixed together. The objective of these working groups was to develop solutions related to the gender-energy nexus in the context of energy transitions, with a long-term perspective set for 2035 and 2050. This process started with the integration of WPs results. Each group's ideas were documented on a shared board and later discussed in a final roundtable session with all participants. The outcomes of this exercise are detailed in Annex 7.

As a final decision, partners agreed to schedule upcoming online meetings in the next few months to continue working on the integration of results and to incorporate further research progress as it becomes available.

7. KEY DECISIONS TAKEN

At the end of the meeting, the team agreed on the following decisions/list of actions:

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

1. Final Conference scheduled for 1-2 weeks of April 2026 in Brussels (led by Portia).
2. Dissemination activities: conduct extensive dissemination efforts throughout the final year of gEneSys.
3. Workshop on pathways to be held in Brussels (date to be defined in June 2025), and organized by Imperial.
4. Workshop with Women in the Energy Sector, targeting participants from the UK, Germany, and Poland (led by UJ).
5. Underperformance of AIMS: discuss challenges and explore possible solutions (Consortium).
6. Scientific publications: all partners must update the consortium on published and planned scientific articles by filling out the dedicated folder "Dissemination & Impact".

8. WAY FORWARD

Commentato [MF2]: Completare @Lucio

9. ANNEX

9.1. ANNEX 4: List of attendees to the project kickoff meeting

IMPERIAL

GENESYS MEETING, LONDON
Imperial College London

Full Name	Affiliation/Organization	February 17 th 2025	February 18 th 2025	Dinner February 18 th 2025	February 19 th 2025
Clemens Stiebing	Fraunhofer IAD	<i>Stiebing</i>	<i>Stiebing</i>	<i>Stiebing</i>	<i>Stiebing</i>
Paulina Sekula	UJ	<i>Sekula</i>	<i>Toussaint Kulk</i>	<i>Toussaint Kulk</i>	<i>Toussaint Kulk</i>
Tadeusz Rudek	UJ	<i>Rudek</i>	<i>Toussaint Kulk</i>	<i>Toussaint Kulk</i>	<i>Toussaint Kulk</i>
Cloe Miranda	CNR	<i>Miranda</i>	<i>Miranda</i>	<i>Miranda</i>	<i>Miranda</i>
Maria Camilla Fraudatario	CNR	<i>Fraudatario</i>	<i>Fraudatario</i>	<i>Fraudatario</i>	<i>Fraudatario</i>
Luca Piscane	CNR	<i>Piscane</i>	<i>Piscane</i>	<i>Piscane</i>	<i>Piscane</i>
Serena Tagliacozzo	CNR	<i>Tagliacozzo</i>	<i>Tagliacozzo</i>	<i>Tagliacozzo</i>	<i>Tagliacozzo</i>
Miriam Tombino	CNR	<i>Tombino</i>	<i>Tombino</i>	<i>Tombino</i>	<i>Tombino</i>
Antonio De Nicola	ENEA	<i>De Nicola</i>	<i>De Nicola</i>	<i>De Nicola</i>	<i>De Nicola</i>
Marta Koch	Imperial	<i>Koch</i>	<i>Koch</i>	<i>Koch</i>	<i>Koch</i>
Rocio Diaz-Chavez	Imperial	<i>Diaz-Chavez</i>	<i>Diaz-Chavez</i>	<i>Diaz-Chavez</i>	<i>Diaz-Chavez</i>
Yara Evans	Imperial	<i>Evans</i>	<i>Evans</i>	<i>Evans</i>	<i>Evans</i>

Elizabeth Pollitzer	Portia	<i>Pollitzer</i>	<i>Pollitzer</i>	<i>Pollitzer</i>	<i>Pollitzer</i>
Gregorio D'Agostino	ENEA	<i>D'Agostino</i>	<i>D'Agostino</i>	<i>D'Agostino</i>	<i>D'Agostino</i>
Ben Pollitzer	Portia	<i>Pollitzer</i>	<i>Pollitzer</i>	<i>Pollitzer</i>	<i>Pollitzer</i>

IMPERIAL

9.2. ANNEX 5: Project Meeting Full Agenda

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

13.00	Registration and light lunch
14.00	WP7/8 - Project status - CNR (30 minutes)
14.30	WP1 – results of the survey with research staff (CNR) (20 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
15:00	WP2 updates – results of the survey + design of case studies (Fraunhofer) (40 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
15:50	WP3 updates – results of the focus groups and forthcoming deliverables (UJ) (30 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
16.30	Coffee break and end of the meeting
16:50	Visit to CO2 capture pilot plant (inside Imperial College)
19.00	Dinner at Ognizko 55 Exhibition Road London SW7 2PG. (Covered by partners)

February 18th

9.00	Coffee and registration
9.30	WP4 updates – forthcoming activities and deliverables (AIMS) (20 minutes) Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
10:00	WP5 – workshop for pathways’ design and policy briefs (Imperial) (40 minutes) Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
10.50	WP6 updates – updates on results Booster, policy paper and final conference (Portia) (20 minutes) Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
11:20	Coffee break
11.50	Autumn School – Venice 5-11 October 2025 (CNR) (dissemination and synergies between modules) (40 minutes + 30 minutes discussion)
13:00	Lunch
14.00	WP 6 Publication
14.30	WP7 – M&E activities, financial reporting
15.00	Visit Energy Centre (leaving from the meeting venue)
19.00	Social Dinner at The Lighterman, 3 Granary Square, London N1C 4BH (covered by Imperial)

9.00	Coffee and registration
9.30	Internal workshop – Integrating WPs results (2,5 hours working in small groups and then plenary)
11.30	Wrap up – open discussion
12:30	Coffee break/light lunch
13:30	End of meeting

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

9.3. ANNEX 6: gEneSys 4th meeting power point presentations on preliminary results

Project Status
gEneSys project meeting London

Where we are:

- We reach 2/3 of our journey
- Much of the research activities have been completed
- Amendment that includes a three month extension: gEneSys will last until April 2026
- We need to consolidate, integrate and create impact around the knowledge produced

Knowledge gathered in 2023/2024

- Ontology
- Knowledge community
- gender energy SHIFT
- Researchers survey
- Citizen survey
- SLR
- Text book
- Focus group
- Case study

Action to create impact and valorise knowledge in 2025

- Policy paper
- Guidelines for curricula
- Guidelines for text books
- Autism School
- EUA Recommendation
- SDG Integration
- Toolbox
- First Conference

Thank You !

T1.5 R&I workforce survey

D.1.3 – A multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder opportunities in sustainable energy systems

Objectives and method

- **Obj:** assess the work climate, organizational culture, work-life balance, and collaboration dynamics within the Research and Innovation (R&I) sector related to the energy system
- **Target group:** researchers, technicians, experts, students engaged in scientific and technological knowledge production for the energy sector
- **Survey characteristics:**
 - Sociodemographic characteristics: gender, age, employment, type of employment contract, work responsibilities, other work
 - Organizational features: energy sector, country, and company size
 - Psychological aspects:
 - Work-related Quality of Life (WRQL) (Eaton & Van Jaen, 2016)
 - Researcher Satisfaction Scale (RSTS) (Eaton et al., 2016)
 - Resilience for job energy resources knowledge production (RJRFP) (Muller Energy Center (MEC) (Eaton et al., 2016))
 - Sampling: random cluster sampling and extended sampling technique
 - Platform for dissemination: Zooming
 - Period: September – November 2024

Research sample information

- 1. 407 respondents (95% response rate)
- 2. 14 EU countries represented and included in the analysis
- 3. 147 respondents engaged in education or training
- 4. Analysis focused on 400 experts in R&I + Research
- 5. 100% female + 11% gender not stated, and 89% not stated nationality code
- 6. 100% EU
- 7. 100% research + 14% industry + 1% other

Method of analysis

- Descriptive statistics
- Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) (WLS, WLS, and MLFAP)
- Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) (WLS, WLS, MLFAP, and PLS) (based on the structure identified by the authors)

Construct name	Constructs	Indicator/Items	α reliability
WRQL	Work-related Quality of Life	1. I am satisfied with my work 2. I am satisfied with my work environment 3. I am satisfied with my work conditions 4. I am satisfied with my work schedule 5. I am satisfied with my work responsibilities 6. I am satisfied with my work relationships 7. I am satisfied with my work opportunities 8. I am satisfied with my work challenges 9. I am satisfied with my work growth 10. I am satisfied with my work security	0.92
RSTS	Researcher Satisfaction	1. I am satisfied with my work 2. I am satisfied with my work environment 3. I am satisfied with my work conditions 4. I am satisfied with my work schedule 5. I am satisfied with my work responsibilities 6. I am satisfied with my work relationships 7. I am satisfied with my work opportunities 8. I am satisfied with my work challenges 9. I am satisfied with my work growth 10. I am satisfied with my work security	0.91
RJRFP	Resilience for job energy resources knowledge production	1. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 2. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 3. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 4. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 5. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 6. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 7. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 8. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 9. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production 10. I am confident in my ability to handle energy resources knowledge production	0.93

• **Cluster Analysis (CA):** seven groups (60% men or more clusters based on assigned factors related to previous section

Respondents profile

- Gender: female (95.0%), male (4.0%)
- Career level: senior (74.7%), middle career (11.8%), and junior (13.5%)
- Education attainment: Bachelor's (79.2%), Master's degree (23%), Doctoral degree (3.4%)
- Field of specialization: engineering, technology, or research in organizations including agencies and public-institutional entities (85.1%), other categories or unspecified (14.9%), not assigned or unspecified or unspecified/unassigned/unassigned (0.0%)
- Type of energy generation method: fossil fuels (46.6%), nuclear (13.1%), renewable energy agency (20.1%), other (19.2%), unspecified or training (10.0%), unknown (1.0%)
- Research profile: Researcher and Technologist (88.2%), Team Manager/Supervisor (11.8%), Director/Leader (0.0%), Research Assistant (0.0%), and other (0.0%). The average "other" (0.0%) includes PhD students (0.4%), administrative positions (0.4%), and project managers, analysts, consultants, and technical specialists (0.0%)
- Team responsibility: Yes (41.7%), No (58.3%). Yes includes children 7-17 years old (28.0%), children 18 years and (10%), elderly relatives (14.0%)

Organizational sector

Cluster Analysis Results

- **Main sectors:** Renewable Energy, Energy Efficiency, Hydrogen, and Energy Storage
- **Researcher activities in generating sustainable energy solutions**
- **Main areas of research & innovation:** solar, wind, energy economics, social and management, and energy policy
- **Research development in R&I:** still less digitalized technology, geothermal energy, waste, and ocean energy

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steerin committee meeting

WRQoL_F1 - Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace

Dimension	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Empowerment	0.65	0.55	0.70	0.60
Goal Clarity	0.60	0.50	0.65	0.55

- Cluster 1 does not feel fully satisfied in terms of a clear objectives, opportunity to make use of their abilities, freedom to voice opinions, and ability to influence decisions.
- Cluster 1 and 3 have more women (20% and 42.1%) than Cluster 2, indicating greater workplace challenges for women.
- Cluster 1 (negative evaluation): fewer researchers in renewables (9.3%), suggesting traditional energy sector value traditional skills less and require conservative practices.

WRQoL_F2 - Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities

Dimension	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Workplace Support	0.60	0.50	0.65	0.55
Professional Development	0.55	0.45	0.60	0.50

- Clusters 2 and 3 report overall satisfaction with their work environment, while Cluster 1 shows negative trends.
- Cluster 1: 50% women, with a negative perception of the workplace, seen as less inclusive and supportive.
- Cluster 3: lower average age (40) and a higher proportion of researchers in the renewable energy sector, which is generally perceived as a more welcoming, inclusive, and stimulating environment.

WRQoL_F3 - Work-Life balance and Flexibility

Dimension	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Work-Life Balance	0.55	0.45	0.60	0.50
Flexibility	0.50	0.40	0.55	0.45

- Disengagement on the presence of flexibility prevail in clusters 2 and 3, while in cluster 1 it seems to be integrated into the working conditions.
- Cluster 1: 30% of women, the average age is 48 years, and 10% work in the renewable energy sector. When flexibility is allowed, an increase in core load is observed, especially for children (24% for 20% and Cluster 2: 17.3% and the elderly (16%).
- In clusters 2 and 3, where women do not benefit from greater flexibility, there is a higher share of women (38.7% and 48.5%), higher presence in the renewable sector (44% and 59.7%), and a more significant core load for children aged 7-17 (24% and 33%).

Discrimination_F1 - Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality

Dimension	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality	0.60	0.50	0.65	0.55

- Cluster 2: agreement on the presence of discrimination dynamics, in contrast to Clusters 1 and 3, where it is largely denied.
- Cluster 2: 50% Researchers (lower than Cluster 1 and 3), and 22% Team Manager/Supervisor (higher than Cluster 1 and 3).
- Women face more challenges in career progression, formal recognition, and workplace impact.

Discrimination_F2 - Perceived Workplace Support and collegiality

Dimension	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Perceived Workplace Support	0.55	0.45	0.60	0.50
Collegiality	0.50	0.40	0.55	0.45

- Cluster 1: Clusters emerge from a supportive work environment (cluster 3: 0.594), to neutral (cluster 1: 0.307), to higher discrimination perceptions (cluster 2: -0.272).
- Cluster 2: Discrimination and limited support
- Researchers work environments, with low job productivity and fewer opportunities for exchange (ideas, feedback and support).
- 34.8% women, 70% researchers, and low participation in the RE (42%).
- Cluster 3: Positive working environment and supportive collegial relationships
- 40% women, average age 43, 65% in the RE
- Focus: 2% Research assistants, 0% Researchers, and 10% Team managers or supervisors.

Discrimination_F3 - Mentorship and Professional Guidance

Dimension	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Mentorship and Professional Guidance	0.55	0.45	0.60	0.50

- Clusters 2 and 3: mainly senior employees (avg. age 48.60% permanent contracts, 70% researchers), show neutral or negative views on mentoring, suggesting it is less relevant for established careers.
- Mentoring & Career Stage: Cluster 1 (avg. age 42) reports the highest mentoring support, with more team managers and supervisors (20%) who may need guidance in early leadership roles.
- Renewables Sector & Mentoring: 62% of Cluster 1 respondents work in renewable energy sector, the highest among clusters, indicating a stronger mentoring culture in the sector. Gender differences do not significantly impact mentoring perceptions.

Discrimination_F4 - Support and Work-Life Balance

Cluster	Age	Gender	Disability	Work-Life Balance
1	20-30	45%	10%	80%
2	31-40	40%	15%	75%
3	41-50	35%	20%	70%
4	51-60	30%	25%	65%
5	61-70	25%	30%	60%

Support in highly skilled to meet requirements especially in Cluster 3 (1.200) and 2 (1.100), where women are 45% and 55%, respectively.

Work-Life Balance & Care Responsibilities: Lack of support in more pronounced in Cluster 1 and 2, where are concentrated care for children (20.8% and 25.8%), and for elderly relatives (25% and 14%).

Positive Perceptions in Cluster 3: Work-life balance is higher (0.5736), fewer women (23%) and lower child/mother ratio (0.15). Care responsibilities significantly lower (0.22%) and children 7 (7 years old) (20%). Most respondents work in renewable energy sector (37%).

Policy_F1 - Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector

Cluster	Age	Gender	Disability	Work-Life Balance
1	20-30	45%	10%	80%
2	31-40	40%	15%	75%
3	41-50	35%	20%	70%
4	51-60	30%	25%	65%
5	61-70	25%	30%	60%

Policy F1 alignment (Cluster 1 - 1.075), agreement (Cluster 2 - 2.802) and mobility (Cluster 3 - 0.200).

Disagreement of Cluster 1: 47% women, average age 48 years, 26% term contract, 74% investment, and 12.26% research activities, 1.6% in R&D sector.

Priority on Job Security: Focus on career stability over inclusion policies.

Openness & Inclusion: High openness to innovation may reduce need for further interventions.

Agreement of Cluster 2: similar to Cluster 1 in composition.

Lower participation in the energy sector, negative strong integration of diversity gender and cultural discrimination in the traditional sector, making inclusive policies most necessary.

Organization_F1 - Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion

Cluster	Age	Gender	Disability	Work-Life Balance
1	20-30	45%	10%	80%
2	31-40	40%	15%	75%
3	41-50	35%	20%	70%
4	51-60	30%	25%	65%
5	61-70	25%	30%	60%

Cluster 2 (Negative Commitment to Diversity): 63% women, reporting a lack of inclusivity and diversity in their workplaces, particularly indicating discriminatory practices, especially affecting women.

Commitment & Coverage: 70% leadership contracts, 70% participation - engagement of diversity management may lead to lower subsequent, especially for women and underrepresented groups.

Cluster 3 (Positive Commitment to Diversity): 21% women, with 63% working in the renewable energy sector, which may promote more inclusive and fair practices.

Renewables & Gender Dynamics: Despite inclusivity in the sector, the low proportion of women in Cluster 3 highlights gender-related issues persist even in progressive sectors.

Summary and Conclusion

- Research in energy systems (sustainable, smart, megaprojects, greenfields, and smart energy)**
- Priority on Job Security:** Focus on career stability over inclusion policies.
- Openness & Inclusion:** High openness to innovation may reduce need for further interventions.
- Agreement of Cluster 2:** similar to Cluster 1 in composition.
- Lower participation in the energy sector,** negative strong integration of diversity gender and cultural discrimination in the traditional sector, making inclusive policies most necessary.
- Work-Life Balance:** A positive work-life balance is associated with higher productivity, reduced absenteeism, and improved retention rates, and lower caregiving burden.
- AI sector as a driver for greater inclusion and equity:** AI sector is a driver for greater inclusion and equity, with AI companies showing more diverse leadership and workforce.

Thank You !

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

WP II
Exploring gendered intersectional patterns in citizen's behaviours and orientations towards the energy transition

Prof. Dr. Martina Schraube, Dr. Clemens Dierckx, Sabina Lutz

Partners: Fraunhofer, ENA, AMGIS, etc.

Goals of WP 2
Gendered and intersectional patterns in energy use and access

- WP 2.1 Quantitative study**
Survey across several countries in Europe and Africa with a total case number of 30,000 respondents, distributed across 10 countries, including 6 EU member states and 4 Sub-Saharan African countries (conducted by a service provider)
- WP 2.2 Co-creation & WP 2.3 Case study**
Delight survey with the expert panel to assess the theoretical understanding of the explored data patterns + Test the applicability of the theoretical framework in concrete cases of the energy transition through 60 interviews with individuals (conducted by the service provider)
- WP 2.4 Policy actions**
Derivation of policy implications tackling intersectional energy injustices in the energy transition

Project progress of WP 2
Data analysis has been finalized, and case studies are in execution

WP2.1 Citizen survey
From mid-October 2024 to mid-January 2025, people aged between 18 and 65/75 were surveyed via an online panel.

Country	Weighting efficiency	Case number
France	76.0%	3200
Germany	77.0%	2600
Italy	67.0%	3217
Poland	66.7%	3000
Portugal	67.0%	3000
Sweden	82.0%	3000
Spain	75.0%	3000
Nigeria	64.0%	3000
South Africa	67.0%	3000
Uganda	58.0%	2500

WP2.1 Citizen survey
No blind spots: a feature of our data is that we analyse participation in the energy system in many different ways.

WP2.1 Citizen survey
Based on the data, we can model very precisely which groups are particularly affected by energy marginalisation.

WP2.1 Citizen survey

Our data can be filled with life using personas. They can be used for political communication and the design of needs-based policies.

Figure 1: The 2016 data results (Global South)

Country	Personas
Kenya	10
India	10
South Africa	10
Spain	10
USA	10
UK	10
Germany	10
France	10
Italy	10
Japan	10
China	10
South Korea	10
Canada	10
Australia	10
Brazil	10
Argentina	10
Chile	10
Colombia	10
Peru	10
Venezuela	10
Mexico	10
Costa Rica	10
Panama	10
Ecuador	10
Bolivia	10
Paraguay	10
Uruguay	10
Guatemala	10
Honduras	10
Nicaragua	10
Cuba	10
Vietnam	10
Thailand	10
Philippines	10
Indonesia	10
Singapore	10
Malaysia	10
Myanmar	10
Laos	10
Cambodia	10
Timor-Leste	10
East Timor	10
Brunei Darussalam	10
Sri Lanka	10
Maldives	10
Bhutan	10
Nepal	10
Bangladesh	10
Pakistan	10
Afghanistan	10
Yemen	10
Sudan	10
Egypt	10
Libya	10
Tunisia	10
Algeria	10
Morocco	10
Senegal	10
Gambia	10
Sierra Leone	10
Liberia	10
Ivory Coast	10
Ghana	10
Upper Volta	10
Niger	10
Chad	10
Cote d'Ivoire	10
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Togo	10
Sierra Leone	10
Liberia	10
Ivory Coast	10
Ghana	10
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Sierra Leone	10
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Ch	

ITALY

Focus groups conducted in Italy (led by CNE)

City	University	Faculty	Participants	Interviews
Genoa	Genoa University	Faculty of Engineering	10	10
Palermo	Palermo University	Faculty of Engineering	10	10
Trieste	Trieste University	Faculty of Engineering	10	10
Udine	Udine University	Faculty of Engineering	10	10
Verona	Verona University	Faculty of Engineering	10	10

Yan, X. (2019). *Energy*. 10(1), 1-10.

SECTORAL IMBALANCE AND EDUCATIONAL CHOICES

STEM FACULTY

- STEM faculty perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM faculty perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM faculty perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.

STEM STUDENTS

- STEM students perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM students perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM students perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.

For both STEM faculty and students, female students show a stronger motivation, but there is a key difference in integration:

STEM FACULTY

- STEM faculty perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM faculty perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM faculty perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.

STEM STUDENTS

- STEM students perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM students perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.
- STEM students perceive gender inequality as a significant barrier to STEM careers.

INTEGRATION OF GENDER

STEM Faculty

- Gender is integrated into curricula.
- The promotion of a culture of equal opportunities is encouraged by the Equal Opportunity Commission.
- Female role models are encouraged to share their experiences and advice.

STEM Students

- There has not yet been full integration.
- Material and funding.
- Qualitative professors are less prepared than students regarding the most innovative approaches.

RECOMMENDATIONS

STEM Faculty

- Quantitative efforts should target females to overcome gender inequality, which increases (former students') choices in their academic paths.

STEM Students

- To convey the idea that energy transition is a multidimensional concept, encompassing both technical and social aspects.
- To work against gender stereotypes in faculties and in school textbooks.

UK

STEM Faculty

- Gender inequality recommendations.
- Marketing approach to attract more students of all genders, using strategies that incorporate role play and experiential aspects of energy (e.g., solar trials and off-peak).

STEM Students

- Focus on the need for changes in course content, rather than curricular content integration.
- Marketing approach to attract more students of all genders, using strategies that incorporate role play and experiential aspects of energy (e.g., solar trials and off-peak).
- Marketing and encourages potentially interested students.

Methodology

Phase	Activities	Tools	Outputs
Preparation	Identify stakeholders, develop research plan, ethics approval	Survey forms, interview guides	Research protocol, ethics approval
Data Collection	Conduct focus groups, distribute surveys	Focus group transcripts, survey data	Raw data, survey responses
Data Analysis	Thematic analysis, statistical analysis	Software (NVivo, SPSS)	Themes, statistical results
Reporting	Write report, present findings	Report template, presentation slides	Final report, presentation

Key Findings Results - I

Key Findings Results - II

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steerin committee meeting

The image displays a series of 15 presentation slides arranged in a grid. The slides are organized into four rows:

- Row 1:**
 - Slide 1: POLAND
 - Slide 2: FGIs in Poland
 - Slide 3: Barriers for Women in the Energy Sector
- Row 2:**
 - Slide 4: Supportive Factors for Women in the Energy Sector
 - Slide 5: Integration of gender dimension in STEM and SDI energy related studies
 - Slide 6: Gendered careers in energy sector
- Row 3:**
 - Slide 7: Next steps
 - Slide 8: Next steps
 - Slide 9: National workshops with female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders
- Row 4:**
 - Slide 10: National workshops with female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders
 - Slide 11: National workshops with female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders
 - Slide 12: Thank You!

WP4 - planning delivery in the reminder of gEneSys

Portia, Elizabeth Pollitzer

Outstanding tasks

- T4.2 Identify the **needs and opportunities** to advance **women in Africa as energy transition researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders** months 15-22
- T4.3 Identify concrete **opportunities, instruments, and mechanisms** to operationalise the European Parliament's recommendations for cooperation on **SDGs implementation** months 25-35
- T4.4 Analyse how the concepts of **equity, inclusion, justice, and fairness** in the context of **SDG7 targets** are interpreted by researchers in Africa months 20-34

WP4-relevant evidence from Elsevier research reported at GS23-Africa

- Research output by volume
- Who funds research
- Which SDGs are most funded
- Women as researchers
- Focus of collaborations with Global North

Do we have useful data relevant to these topics from gEneSys studies?

African scholarly output has increased by 76% on average in the period 2017- 2021 vs. 2013-2017

- SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) is by far the area with most research output. This is in line with the global trend.
- It has grown by 81% in 2017-2021 vs. 2013-2017.
- Africa has more than doubled its research output on SDG 7. This remains the second largest area, from a volume perspective.
- (Could not find more data has been disaggregated by sex)

The gaps to world averages of women's participation in SDG research seems to be addressed through Global North – Africa collaboration (not for SDG4 and 5)

Note very low participation of women in relation to SDG4 globally and in GN-Africa collaboration

Distribution of African SDG research funded by top African funders

- Across the board, and following the global trend, most of African funding agencies focus on funding health related research (SDG3)
- The second area of focus is SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy)
- There are also funding agencies focusing on specific areas such as SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and Government of Kenya (SDG) or SDG 4 (Quality Education)
- Note the strong focus on health and energy

Introducing Scopus AI

T4.2 Identify the needs and opportunities to advance women in Africa as energy transition researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders

Question for Scopus:
What are the needs and opportunities to advance women in Africa as energy transition researchers

Deeper questions suggested by Scopus 1:

- What initiatives or programmes are currently in place to empower and advance women in energy transition research in Africa
- What are the key challenges faced by women in Africa pursuing career in energy transition research?
- How can the energy sector in Africa be more inclusive and supportive of women in research and innovation?

Deeper questions suggested by Scopus 2:

- What are the opportunities for collaboration between women in energy transition research across different African countries
-etc

Elements of Scopus AI results

- The question
- Keyword search query
- Summary: Needs, Opportunities, Challenges
- Extended Summary
- Conceptual Map
- Topic experts
- Emerging themes
- Go deeper (several levels)
- References used for the summary
- Foundational documents
- Citations
- Conclusions

Revised delivery strategy for T4.2, 4.3, 4.4

- **Scopus AI**
 - Translate T4.2 (a priority), then T4.3 and T4.4 into questions
 - Could identify topic experts (for dissemination)
 - Could identify emerging issues
- **Other questions?**
 - Select from Energy SHIFTS questions
 - Select from GS23 presentations
- **Disseminate to:**
 - AAS: The African Research Initiative for Scientific Excellence (ARISE)
 - SGC: Science granting agencies in Africa
 - LEAP-RE: consortia partners
 - WAAW
- **Publish** in Scientific African, South African Journal of Science, Int. J. of Scientific in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology

IMPERIAL

IMPERIAL SA Co creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology Task Leader: IC, Contributors: Paris, CNR, ENEA, IRENEZ

- This task will address existing issues with low adaptability for the co-creation of credible and consistent pathways that further guide power producers and provide a fair and just energy transition.
- The resulting energy system for 2050 will be the result of the iterative energy backcasting process. The resulting energy system will be the result of the iterative energy backcasting process. The resulting energy system will be the result of the iterative energy backcasting process.
- The task will address existing issues with low adaptability for the co-creation of credible and consistent pathways that further guide power producers and provide a fair and just energy transition.

IMPERIAL

Energy transition pathways to 2050: development of flexible, operational and policy-ready pathways, which capture and reflect a set of shared values (EN, 2020)

IMPERIAL

Examples of pathways

- Global Energy Assessment, 2013
- Pathways (quantities and qualitative description) of forward and supply side energy system technologies being used to generate the energy technology needed to meet a pathway in: USA, Europe, USA, and EU, Africa.

IMPERIAL

Back Technological

Technology	Year	Capacity (GW)	Cost (€/MWh)
Coal	2020	1000	100
Nuclear	2020	500	100
Gas	2020	1000	100
Wind	2020	100	100
Solar	2020	100	100
Hydro	2020	100	100
Batteries	2020	10	100
Hydrogen	2020	10	100
Coal	2050	0	0
Nuclear	2050	500	100
Gas	2050	0	0
Wind	2050	1000	100
Solar	2050	1000	100
Hydro	2050	100	100
Batteries	2050	100	100
Hydrogen	2050	100	100

IMPERIAL

Example criteria and indicators topic Employment and Economic Participation

- Renewable Employment & Energy Sector**
 - Number and percentage of workers employed in renewable energy sectors (solar, wind, hydrogen, etc.)
 - Number and percentage of workers employed in the energy sector
- Renewable Energy**
 - Renewable energy capacity (GW)
 - Renewable energy production (TWh)
 - Renewable energy investment (€)
- Renewable Energy Distribution**
 - Renewable energy capacity (GW)
 - Renewable energy production (TWh)
 - Renewable energy investment (€)
- Renewable Energy Distribution**
 - Renewable energy capacity (GW)
 - Renewable energy production (TWh)
 - Renewable energy investment (€)

IMPERIAL

Backcasting

"The major distinguishing characteristic of backcasting analysis is a concern, not with what *is* and *is likely to happen*, but with how *desired* futures can be achieved. It is this that specifies our method. Involving working backwards from a particular desirable future and asking the question in order to determine the physical feasibility of that future and what policy measures would be required to reach that point" (Robinson, 1990; also in Robinson 2003).

"Typically backcasting is applied on long term complex issues, involving many aspects of society as well as technological innovation and change. The focus of interest is not a particular specific problem of great importance such as the vast and growing impacts of transport on the environment. It is not a specific problem that this is a niche for backcasting."

IMPERIAL

Backcasting gives you a chance to look through the lens of desired future vision to the real world, as well as the lens to imagine the best possible scenario where you could arrive and then it is about imagining a very clear future not constrained by the limits of what is possible. This concept is a form of 'top-down' thinking, not 'bottom-up' thinking.

"There is a danger that you may identify the future state of possibility that you have the best chance of achieving. This is not the case. The future state of possibility that you have the best chance of achieving is the one that you have the best chance of achieving."

Backcasting gives you a chance to look through the lens of desired future vision to the real world, as well as the lens to imagine the best possible scenario where you could arrive and then it is about imagining a very clear future not constrained by the limits of what is possible. This concept is a form of 'top-down' thinking, not 'bottom-up' thinking.

IMPERIAL

Forecasting and backcasting the limits.

Forecasting	Backcasting
1. Predictable	1. Uncertain
2. Stable	2. Dynamic
3. Linear	3. Non-linear
4. Short-term	4. Long-term
5. Top-down	5. Bottom-up

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

The collage consists of several presentation slides from the IMPERIAL project steering committee meetings. The slides are arranged in a grid-like fashion, with some overlapping. The top row includes slides titled 'IMPERIAL' with bullet points, 'Backcasting in the MLE, following the A-B-C-D method developed by The Natural Step?', and 'Example with citizen science'. The middle row features 'Workshops' with a list of activities, a slide with a globe and text, and a slide with a grid of icons. The bottom row includes a 'Thank You!' slide with logos for IMPERIAL, ENZ, and other partners. The slides are predominantly green and white, with some blue and red accents.

WP6 – Dissemination Mechanisms

Dissemination network

- EUSEW (proposal on policy session)
- LEAP-RE (joint webinar, platform, direct communications with lead partners)
- EURIEC (European Research Centres on Renewable Energy, European Masters in Renewable Energy, they are starting new project on gender with U. Paris)
- Session at the African Conference of Women in Science and Engineering organised by AIMS
- IEBA (European Energy Research Alliance, discussing a joint webinar, participation in Venice, and final conference)
- CESAR (participation in EUSEW panel)
- Horizon Europe/FP10 Advisory Group (communication on the 4 questions)
- Energy Shifts (frequent communications/invitations, etc)
- ZENEDO
- Joint Conference with NET44e
- Final Conference

Final Conference

- Need a date: 2nd or 3rd week in April
- We could dovetail it to the INSPIRE (inclusive gender equality in R&I) final conference which will be in Brussels on 16-17 April?
- Need a theme. How about: *Gendered Dimensions of Power and Inequality in Energy Transition. New Evidence and Analysis from the gEneSys project for Equitable, Fair and Just Outcomes* (Portia is organizing the INSPIRE conference, so will have to come up with a complimentary theme)
- Keynote speakers: Commission, Advisory Group,
- Format: Half day report on research + half day on policy, round table sessions.....

Horizon Europe Results Booster Service

Proposed roadmap

Milestone (deliverable)	Timing
2.2 EUSEW - Milestone A - Call off	March 2025
2.2 EUSEW - Milestone B - Strategic Value Proposition (SVP) & Key exploitable results (KERs)	April 2025
2.2 EUSEW - Milestone C - Exploitation Strategy	May 2025
2.2 Milestone F - Reporting	June 2025

To be considered during next monitoring call + 2.2 Dissemination

We will be with you during the whole project delivery, starting with this road meeting. With the Follow-Up Support (2.2 FUS) we will take the dissemination effort and the leading results.

B*OSTER

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

gEneSys Autumn School
6 - 10 October 2025

Number of applications received so far: 40

- Spain: 1
- Sweden: 3
- Switzerland: 1
- Germany (North Rhine-Westphalia): 1
- Italy: 1
- Belgium: 1
- USA: 2
- South Korea: 2
- Poland: 2
- China: 1
- UK: 1
- Denmark: 1
- Finland: 1
- Canada: 1
- France: 1
- Spain: 1
- Central European University: 1
- Belgium: 1
- Turkey: 1
- Polymath: 1

Please further promote the school among your network!

Logistics info for partners:

84 euros approx. per night for accommodation in San Servolo Island provided by VIU – on each partner's budget

VIU is expecting a first confirmation on dates for partners' participation by July (3 months in advance) – final dates 1 month prior

Country	Partner	Application Date	Status
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
Germany (North Rhine-Westphalia)
Italy
Belgium
USA
South Korea
Poland
China
UK
Denmark
Finland
Canada
France
Spain
Central European University
Belgium
Turkey
Polymath

DAY 1: ENSA - "Conceptual foundations of the Energy System and gendered analysis of the energy transition scientific community"

This module explores the foundations of energy system ontology, focusing on five key subsystems: environment, strategy, policy, behavior, and operation. It examines ontology design patterns and the interdependencies of these subsystems, emphasizing the sector's complexity.

The second part addresses the scientific community in energy transition research through a gendered lens, focusing on data collection, semantic analysis, social network building, and creating gender gaps. Participants will use quantitative and qualitative tools and engage in interactive activities to translate theoretical concepts into practical strategies for addressing gender disparities.

DAY 2. Fraunhofer IAO - "Creating Data-Driven and Human-Centered Policies for a Just Energy Transition"

This module explores the complexities of energy justice, using insights from the gEneSys survey of 30,000 citizens across the EU and Sub-Saharan Africa. Participants will examine how energy systems affect social groups differently, focusing on issues like energy poverty, health impacts, and value-driven energy choices. Key topics include the presentation of data-driven analyses of marginalization in energy policy and foundational concepts drawing on theories such as social and energy justice, feminist political ecology, and science and technology studies to design truly just energy systems." Through a policy-making exercise based on real-world personas, participants will design targeted strategies to address energy justice challenges. The seminar follows the SEE (sensitization, equipping, empowerment) approach, combining interactive learning, theoretical insights, and competitive group work to empower participants in creating equitable energy policies.

DAY 4 Jagiellonian University - "Shaping Sustainable Futures: Gender, Policy, and Research in the Energy Education"

This module explores the intersection of ethics, innovation, and gender in the energy sector. It begins with a 30-minute introduction on co-creating innovation through gender perspectives, followed by a 90-minute lecture on the Gendered Innovation framework and case studies showcasing gender analysis in energy solutions. In workshops, participants will identify gender biases in energy education materials and develop inclusive high school modules, such as gendered energy use, energy careers, and mainstreaming gender in energy innovation. Teams will present their projects for feedback. The module aims to enhance understanding of the Gendered Innovations framework, the gender-energy nexus, and strategies for creating inclusive, engaging curricula.

DAY 5 Imperial - "Engendering Energy Just and Fair Pathways"

This module aims to equip participants with tools to integrate the gender innovation framework into research and policy, using the SHFT's project as an example. It covers how energy pathways are developed and how to apply gender-sensitive criteria and indicators in the design of socio-technical systems for energy transition. Through the analysis of existing energy pathways, including the Net Zero model, participants will learn the importance of incorporating gender and social inequality factors to ensure a just energy transition. The module includes practical exercises, including using AI to design gender-inclusive energy pathways, and participatory methods such as group activities, discussions, and hands-on exercises with technology to create pathways that promote gender equality.

DAY 3. CNR-IRPPS - "TRANSFORM LAB: Interrelations of Power in Energy Transition"

This module applies the Transformative Power Lab model to explore power dynamics within the energy transition and develop tools for fostering equitable transformations. Participants will examine the five layers of the energy system—environment, strategy, policy, behavior, and operation—through the gEneSys ontology framework. The first part covers theoretical foundations of power dynamics, introducing concepts like 'power to,' 'power over,' and 'power with,' to build power literacy. In the second part, participants engage in workshops, analyzing power relations within specific layers and exploring strategies to enable just transformations. This hands-on approach equips participants with analytical and strategic skills to influence equitable energy transition policies and innovations.

DAY 4. AIMS & Portia - "Opportunities, Instruments, and Mechanisms to Improve Social Impact of the EU-Africa REU co-operative efforts an energy transition by mainstreaming gender into design and implementation strategies"

This module will explore the EU policies shaping EU-Africa cooperation on energy transition, focusing on how gender can be mainstreamed in the design and implementation strategies. Participants will identify key challenges in integrating gender into EU-Africa research and innovation partnerships. The module will also highlight opportunities to strengthen efforts to advance the role of women in Africa as researchers, innovators, and entrepreneurs. Finally, it will promote innovative solutions aimed at creating greener, more digital, and healthier societies in Africa, driving inclusive growth and development in the context of the energy transition.

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

gEneSys
Publication plan

Provisional Title	Journal considered	Deadline	Lead
Shaping Energy Systems: Societal Acceptance of Just and Sustainable Energy Transitions	Environmental Innovation and Sustainable Transitions	June 2025	IMJ (Subini)
Improving Fair Value-based Disaggregation of Gender in Scientific Communities	Scientometrics	2nd review round	ENEA
The Energy System Ontology: Addressing the Multi-Dimensional Challenges of Energy Transition	Energy Research & Social Science	1st review round	ENEA
Women's Resilience in the Time of Covid-19	Journal of Gender Studies	Published	ENEA
Gender Gap in the Critical Infrastructure Research Community	Journal of Energy Transition	To appear	ENEA
Gender-Aware Business Process Management	Post-proceedings of IACS 2024 conference	To appear	ENEA

Provisional Title	Journal considered	Deadline	Lead
Gender's Energy Transition Pathway Through a Gender Lens: An Analysis of Recovery and Resilience Plans	Energy Research and Social Science	To appear	IMJ
A multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems	Special Issue Journal of Gender Studies	March, 29, 2025	CNR
Gender gaps in research and innovation for the energy transition: STEM and 50+ universities, in-depth studies and the vision of teachers in Italy, Germany and UK	Humanities and Social Science Communication	March 28th, 2025	CNR
TSD - Paper: Measuring energy justice through the capability approach	Energy Justice	August 31, 2025	IMJ, CNR
TSD - Paper: The interplay between Technological Solutions and Resilience	TBD	TBD	IMJ (Subini)
Gender Gaps in the Energy Transition Research Community	TBD	TBD	ENEA

Provisional Title	Journal considered	Deadline	Lead
Towards an Ontology for Safe Gender-Aware Business Process Management	2025 International Conference on Safety & Innovation (ICSI)	To appear	ENEA
Towards a Maturity Framework for Gender Awareness of Business Process Management	9th ISReDA Service	Submitted	ENEA
Planning the gender-energy nexus: a grey literature review	Current Research in Environmental Sustainability	April 30th, 2025	AJ

gEneSys Monitoring and Evaluation

Survey results – February 2025

Dimensions

1. Information sharing and collaboration within the consortium
2. Adaptation capacity
3. Distribution of resources
4. Involvement of early career researchers
5. Outreach
6. Impact and future directions

Results (as of February 2025 – third round)

39 responses (lower than other rounds)

Dimension 1. Information sharing and collaboration within the consortium

3a Since the project's onset, how frequently did you experience bottlenecks in the sharing of information and reports within the consortium?

9 NOT AT ALL, 1 SOMETIMES

3b Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that different working practices have created bottlenecks in the delivery of the project's activities?

4 NOT AT ALL, 4 SOMETIMES

Results

Dimension 2. Adaptation Capacity

2a Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to respond well to the changing circumstances within the consortium (e.g., new people added)?

9 YES, 1 MISSING

2b Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to adapt well to the changing circumstances outside the consortium (e.g., new inputs from emergent research)?

9 YES, 1 MISSING

Results

Dimension 3. Distribution of resources

3a Do you think that the project consortium have (NOT) had been able to fit its budget with the membership amongst partners? **1 YES, 1 MISSING, 4 NOT AT ALL**

3b Since the project's onset, did you perceive to be able to take full advantage from the resources made available by the consortium (e.g., funds to attend conferences, opportunities to report professional experience)? **1 YES, 4 NOT AVAILABLE**

3c For EC partners only: how in the project's onset, how often did you perceive the benefits arising from your involvement in the consortium? **1 VERY FREQUENTLY, 2 FREQUENTLY, 3 SOMETIMES, 4 NOT AT ALL**

3d Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive that greater interactions between consortium members with resources outside project have influenced the way in which project's activities have been carried out? **1 NOT AT ALL, 4 SOMETIMES**

Results

Dimension 4. Involvement of early career researchers

4a Do you think that only how many early career researchers work on the project's activities or your team/early career researchers should have no more than their own institutional hierarchy?

Not responses: 2 YES, 0 NO, 0 D

4b Do you think that only how many early career researchers work on the project's activities or your team/early career researchers should have no more than their own institutional hierarchy?

2 very frequently, 1 frequently and 1 sometimes

4c Do you think that only how many early career researchers work on the project's activities or your team/early career researchers should have no more than their own institutional hierarchy?

2 not at all, 4 sometimes, 1 frequently

9.4. ANNEX 7: gEneSys 4th meeting power point presentations – Internal workshop

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

The collage contains several key documents:

- gEneSys Project Meeting**: 17th-18th February 2025, Imperial College London, Grantham Institute for Climate Change and the Environment Boardroom.
- Imperial College**: Information regarding the project's location and contact details.
- Internal workshop agenda**: A detailed schedule for the project's internal workshops.
- Small groups**: A table listing the names and members of the project's working groups.
- The evaluators' vision of the gEneSys impact**: A list of nine key impact areas, such as 'gender equality as a lever for better than a barrier for energy transition'.
- Accordingly, a credible energy transition pathway could be one that**: A list of five guiding principles for a credible energy transition, including 'Recognises gender equality as a lever (enabler) rather than a barrier'.
- Let's reflect: group exercise**: A set of reflective questions for the project team.
- WPI Results**: A summary of the project's progress and key findings.
- WP2**: A detailed report on the second work package, including objectives and activities.

Grey Literature

- Identifying gendered patterns of energy consumption in households, workplaces and public spaces,
- Collecting evidence on gender inequalities in access to energy services and energy labour
- Identifying gaps in the reflection on gender-energy nexus

FGIs

- Energy dispressed among subjects - No information about job opportunities during education
- No information about energy related social practices in everyday life
- Women in **academia** (less profitable), men in **industry** (higher salaries)
- Women researchers into **fundamental/basic research**, men into **applied research**
- Renewable energy** as more attractive/accessible for women
- Women as tokens** in management of energy companies

Text books

- Innovation and scientific research illustrated by images of men
- Energy issues are thought in abstract manner, as gender neutral phenomenon
- Information about fossil fuels and renewables (mainly wind, hydropower, sun)
- gender- energy nexus is not discussed at all
- No focus on energy as a career path
- No reflection on practices – systemic outlook

Internal Workshop

Accordingly, a credible energy transition pathway could be one that:

- a) recognises gender equality as a lever (enabler), rather than a barrier
- b) promotes actions designed to produce gender equality benefits
- c) uses gender knowledge to create solutions to related societal challenges
- d) recognises different populations and their special needs
- e) promotes coordinated mainstreaming of gender across relevant policies
- f) advances girls and women as active drivers and agents of progress
- g) recognises gaps in research and helps fill them in
- h) supports the efforts of the UN Women (and similar bodies)

The evaluators' vision of the gEneSys impact (extracted from their report)

1. gender equality as lever for (rather than a barrier to) energy transition
2. gender equality as an outcome of energy transition efforts
3. gender equality connected to the EU Green Deal; climate change mitigation; and SDG implementation agendas/needs
4. results are relevant to a variety of different population
5. gender mainstreaming is harmonised and coordinated into energy transition policies.
6. girls and women play active role in the transition to carbon-neutrality
7. all target groups are well identified
8. research gaps are identified
9. UN women offices are target for dissemination

Let's reflect: group exercise

- What research we already have in the gEneSys collection of evidence, and what information/understanding we still need, to confirm the evaluators' expectations of the project's impact
- Is the 'credible pathway' based on the evaluators' expectations a good start
- What questions to ask Scopus AI to get a better grounding?

- Energy transition can produce new or reinforce existing vulnerabilities
- Gender disaggregated data are not available in the energy sectors
- Policies supporting energy transitions are gender blind and should be more aware of gender and social impacts they produce
- Energy related training curricula are not encouraging a sociotechnical approach to energy, to achieve this there is the need for interdisciplinary in STEM education

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

First outcome – Internal workshop

gEneSys consortium in London

101094326 – GeneSys – D.7.8

Summary/outline of the 3rd and 4th steering committee meeting

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